

THE INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH GROUP ON WOOD PROTECTION

Guidelines for the preparation of a Poster Paper and Poster Presentation at an IRG Scientific Conference

NB

Please note that papers received after the deadline 1 March 2025 will be posted on the website (Compendium) but the opportunity to make an oral presentation will be at the discretion of the Scientific Programme Committee chair. These papers may be presented as posters at the meeting. Deadline for submitting extended abstract or short papers for poster presentations is 1 April 2025.

**IRG SECRETARIAT
Drottning Kristinas v. 61B
SE-114 86 Stockholm
Sweden
www.irg-wp.com**

Dear author of the IRG poster/paper!

Allocation of the papers to different sections is one of the most challenging tasks for the Scientific Programme Committee (SPC). In order to prepare good programme for the upcoming conference, we would like to ask you for assistance. Please tick, the most appropriate Working Party, where your paper fits most. SPC will try to consider your opinion.

Section 1. Biology	WP 1.1. Microorganisms	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 1.2. Insects & Marine borers	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 1.3. Natural Durability	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 1.4. Microbial test methodology	<input type="checkbox"/>
Section 2. Wood Protection	WP 2.1. Wood preservatives	x
	WP 2.2. Fire retardants	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 2.3. Other protecting chemicals	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 2.4. Treatability of wood & quality control of processes and materials	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 2.5. Wood protection by design & new protection concepts	<input type="checkbox"/>
Section 3. Wood Modification	WP 3.1. Thermal modification	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 3.2. Chemical modification	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 3.3. Other penetrating modifications	x
	WP 3.4. Surface modification	<input type="checkbox"/>
Section 4. Applications and Performance	WP 4.1. Laboratory and field performance	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 4.2. Service life	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 4.3. Wood-based Composites	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 4.4. Analysis and Standards	<input type="checkbox"/>
Section 5. Sustainability and Environment	WP 5.1. Health and Safety Aspects	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 5.2. Reuse and recyclability of treated or modified wood	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 5.3. Environmental Impact	<input type="checkbox"/>
	WP 5.4. Circular economy of wood products	<input type="checkbox"/>

This paper is intended for:

- x Short oral (3 min., 1-3 slides) + poster presentation
 Poster presentation only

This poster paper will most probably be presented by:

Rene Herrera

renealexander.herrera@ehu.eus

This paper will be listed as part of the Proceedings according to Thomson-Reuters index system.

OVERVIEW OF PREPARING A POSTER AND A POSTER PAPER

A poster is a graphically based approach to presenting research. The standard format of a poster should generally follow the same format as the full scientific presentation and generally includes: Title/Authors/Affiliations, Introduction, Materials and Methods (Experimental Design or Procedures), Results and Discussion, Conclusions/Recommendations; A poster should be concise in wording and should not contain all the detailed information about the subject. You should aim to use the poster as a means for generating active discussion of the research studies. Scientific posters should stimulate interest rather than provide a detailed presentation. Since there will be multiple posters that will be shown, you need to make sure to use more “visuals” (graphs, photographs, schematics, maps, etc.) to make your poster interesting and visually attractive to the viewers.

A poster shall always be accompanied by a poster paper shaped as a 2-4 pages extended abstract based on the template and Guidelines for the preparation of a full scientific paper IRG 20-60447(see also pages 5-8 in this document).

General guidelines:

- The relevance of the poster for IRG meetings must be germane to wood protection research or wood protection industry.
- Plan the layout of your poster beforehand. Place the title/Authors/Affiliations at the top. Start with the Introduction at the upper left, finish with the conclusions/recommendations at the lower right, with Materials and Methods (Experimental Design or Procedures), Results and Discussion filling the central space.
- Use short sentences, simple words, and bullets to illustrate your points.
- Text should be broken up by including visuals, such as graphs, photographs, schematics, maps, etc. along with colour decorations
- Self-explanatory graphics should dominate the poster. The success of a poster directly relates to the clarity of your illustrations and tables!
- Avoid using jargon, acronyms, or unusual abbreviations.
- The poster (text and graphics) should be easily readable from a distance of about 2 metres. As a thumb rule, the text should be readable if the poster is printed out on an A4 sheet (e.g. Arial >24 points).

Title: Title should be in large fonts and attract potential viewers. If possible, include author names, institute logos or affiliations in smaller size and put in below the title.

Introduction: Precisely present the issue or question or topic to get your viewers interested while using the absolute minimum of background information and definitions. Be sure to include objectives of your study at the end of your introduction.

Materials and Methods: Be short, but precise. State what study design you used and define experimental design. Provide a case definition, if applicable. Mention statistical, laboratory and other methods that were used.

Results and Discussion: Briefly provide descriptive results. Present data that more specifically addresses the hypothesis and refer to supporting charts or images. Tables and graphs should stand on their own. Discuss your results in precise and concise way.

Conclusion and/or Recommendations: Comment on main results and demonstrate why they are conclusive and interesting. What are your recommendations for future studies?

Making the poster

- Give yourself ample time to prepare a poster, and generally plan for about 1-2 weeks ahead.
- Make it obvious to the viewer how to progressively view the poster. The poster generally should read from left to right, and top to bottom. Numbering the individual panels, or connecting them with arrows, is a standard "guidance system" (An Example as shown below).
- Usually a presentation software such as PowerPoint will be used. Format your PowerPoint slide on the size you'll like to have it printed (e.g. 90x130 cm) by using the menu data -> format page. You can insert your text and graphics directly on that slide or copy-paste it from a Word document or a PowerPoint slide.
- Print the poster in an A4 format to check for layout, colors, font size and spelling errors before printing it in large size.
- After the poster is printed in large format, changes are no longer possible.
- **It is recommended to have some handouts of your poster for distribution during the session.**

IRG 25-YYXXX

THE INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH GROUP ON WOOD PROTECTION

Section Y

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Evaluation of Oak bark extracts as bio-based preservative agents in wood protection

Rene Herrera¹, Amina Selmanovic^{1,2,3}, Faksawat Poochajai^{2,4}, Cristina Peña¹, Anna Sandak^{2,3,5}

¹ Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain.

² InnoRenew CoE, 6310 Izola, Slovenia.

³ Faculty of mathematics, natural sciences, and information technologies; University of Primorska, 6000 Koper, Slovenia.

⁴ School of Chemical Engineering, Department of Bioproducts and Biosystems, Aalto University, 00076 Aalto, Finland.

⁵ Andrej Marušič Institute, University of Primorska, 6000 Koper, Slovenia.

Poster paper prepared for the IRG56 Scientific Conference on Wood Protection
Yokohama, Japan
22 - 26 June, 2025

Disclaimer

The opinions expressed in this document are those of the author(s) and are not necessarily the opinions or policy of the IRG Organization.

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SE-114 86 Stockholm
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Rene Herrera^{1a}, Amina Selmanovic^{1b,2,3}, Faksawat Poohphajai^{2,4}, Cristina Peña^{1c}, Anna Sandak^{2,3,5}

¹Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain. ^a renealexander.herrera@ehu.eus ^b aselmanovi001@ikasle.ehu.eus ^c cristina.pr@ehu.eus

²InnoRenew CoE, 6310 Izola, Slovenia. anna.sandak@inorenew.eu

³Faculty of mathematics, natural sciences, and information technologies; University of Primorska, 6000 Koper, Slovenia.

⁴School of Chemical Engineering, Department of Bioproducts and Biosystems, Aalto University, 00076 Aalto, Finland. faksawat.poohphajai@aalto.fi

⁵Andrej Marušič Institute, University of Primorska, 6000 Koper, Slovenia.

abstract

Bark represents a major by-product of the forestry sector and is often referred to low value uses such as combustion for energy, soil mulching or animal bedding. Nevertheless, bark contains a wide array of bioactive constituents, offering considerable potential for transformation into value-added wood protection agents. Developing sustainable wood treatments based on these natural compounds aligns with circular economy principles and reduces dependence on synthetic biocides. In this study, selected bark extracts were explored for their antifungal activity against common wood-degrading fungi to assess their suitability for eco-friendly wood preservation strategies. Residual wet outer oak bark (*Quercus robur*) was dried, milled and subjected to three extractions methods: aqueous, organic solvent, and alkaline. A rotary evaporator was used for aqueous extraction, ultrasonic-assisted extraction (UAE) for the organic solvent, and a pressure reactor for the alkaline process. The extracts were physicochemical characterized and formulated into water-based treatment solutions, which were applied to wood specimens via vacuum-pressure impregnation. Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) and beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) samples were treated and evaluated for leachability and resistance against white and brown rot fungi. Results showed differences in extract concentration and composition, depending on the extraction method. Alkaline extraction yielded the highest concentrations, while aqueous and solvent extractions were lower. Regarding the wood impregnation, treatments containing alkaline-based extracts exhibited higher leachability than the other two extracts, which showed similar performance. Fungal decay resistance varied by wood species. In *P. sylvestris*, solvent extracts treatments were particularly effective, with no visible degradation by *Rhodonina placenta* or *Trametes versicolor*. In *F. sylvatica*, all treatments reduced decay from *R. placenta* or *T. versicolor* compared to controls, with complete inhibition of *R. placenta* by the solvent extracts and reduced decay from both fungal strains with alkaline extracts. This research highlights the potential of bark waste as a valuable bioresource for sustainable wood protection. However, further optimization of extract concentration and impregnation parameters is needed to enhance stability and long-term antifungal efficacy.

Keywords: Bark extracts, wood protection, bio-based preservative, fungal decay resistance

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for sustainable materials and the need to manage forestry residues have driven research toward valorizing side streams and by-products from wood processing. Among these, bark represents a major residual fraction, typically used for low-value applications such as energy generation, soil mulching, or animal bedding (Pasztor *et al.* 2016). However, bark contains significantly higher amounts of extractives than wood, including polyphenolic compounds with known biological activity (Ferreira *et al.* 2015; Dedrie *et al.* 2015).

Oak bark (*Quercus robur*) is rich in both hydrolysable and condensed tannins, along with flavonoids and phenolic acids. These compounds have demonstrated antioxidant, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antifungal properties, which make them ideal components for bio-based wood protection systems (Drózd and Pyszynska 2018). Moreover, tannins are historically used in leather tanning, however they have potential for broader applications, including fire retardancy and wood preservation (Phan 2020).

The effectiveness of polyphenol extraction depends on factors including tree species, bark age, and extraction method. Conventional solvents like ethanol, methanol, and acetone are often used, but adding water enhances extraction efficiency by disrupting solute-matrix bonds. Hot water and alkaline extractions are also widely applied to recover polyphenolic compounds, though alkaline extraction typically results in higher yields and produces extracts with lower viscosity (Borrega *et al.* 2022). Moreover, organic solvents are advantageous for their ease of recovery and compatibility with industrial processes (Torres-Ortiz *et al.* 2024).

Sustainability concerns regarding conventional wood preservatives, many of which are toxic and fossil-based, highlight the need for renewable and safer alternatives. The bioactive compounds extracted from bark can be formulated into treatment solutions and impregnated into wood under vacuum-pressure conditions. This process facilitates deep penetration of active substances into the wood matrix, enhancing protection against biological agents such as fungi and bacteria, as well as abiotic factors like moisture and UV exposure (Tuominen 2023). Bark-based treatments thus present an environmentally friendly alternative, especially as the construction sector continues to expand and demands materials with lower environmental impact and improved durability.

In this context, oak bark emerges as a promising source of natural preservatives. The objective of this study was to extract and characterize bioactive compounds from residual oak bark using aqueous, solvent, and alkaline extraction methods, and to evaluate their potential as sustainable wood treatments by assessing leachability and antifungal efficacy against common wood-decay fungi.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

Residual wet outer bark of *Quercus robur* (oak) was collected and processed for the extraction. The bark material was air-dried, milled, sieved (mesh N°10), and then conditioned at 20°C and 65%RH and stored in a dry dark environment until use. Three extraction methods were applied: aqueous, organic solvent, and alkaline aqueous extraction.

2.2 Extraction methods

Three extraction methods were applied to the conditioned *Quercus robur* bark: (a) Hot water extraction was performed using a rotary evaporator under vacuum at a controlled temperature for 1 hour. (b) Organic solvent extraction was conducted via ultrasonic-assisted extraction (UAE) using a 60:40 ethanol–water mixture. The extraction was carried out for 15 minutes with an ultrasonic probe, maintaining a maximum temperature of 60 °C. (c) Alkaline aqueous extraction was performed with 1% NaOH solution for 60 minutes at 90 °C in a closed pressure reactor. Extraction yields were calculated for each method, and all extraction conditions were optimized in preliminary tests.

2.3 Extracts characterization

The concentration of the extracts was determined gravimetrically. Total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid content (TFC) were analysed using spectrophotometric methods. TPC was measured using the Folin–Ciocalteu assay, with results expressed as gallic acid equivalents (mg GAE per gram of bark). TFC was determined using the aluminium chloride colorimetric method, with quercetin as the calibration standard, and results expressed as quercetin equivalents (mg QE per gram of raw extract).

2.4 Wood impregnation

Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) and beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) samples were vacuum-pressure impregnated with the prepared bio-based solutions at room temperature. Different impregnation times were applied depending on the wood species and treatment. After impregnation, the samples were cured at 103°C to ensure fixation of the active compounds. Leachability tests were conducted on the cured specimens to evaluate the stability and retention of the impregnated extracts.

2.5 Biological durability tests

Decay resistance was evaluated following exposure to *Rhodonia placenta* (brown rot) and *Trametes versicolor* (white rot). Treated and control samples were placed in jars containing fungal mycelium and incubated in darkness at (22 ± 2) °C and (70 ± 5) % relative humidity for 8 weeks. After incubation, samples were visually inspected for mycelial overgrowth. Post-exposure, the specimens were weighed to record the wet mass and subsequently oven-dried at 103 °C until reaching a constant weight. Mass loss was calculated as an indicator of fungal degradation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Extracts characterization

The chemical characterization of the bark extracts revealed clear differences in pH, concentration, and polyphenolic content depending on the extraction method (Table 1). Hot water extraction had the most acidic solution the lowest concentration of extractables. Moreover, the TPC and TFC in this extract was approximately 20–30% of the values obtained from the ethanol–water extract, which proved to be the most efficient in recovering phenolics and flavonoids. Alkaline extraction resulted in the highest overall concentration of solubilized bark material, although its TPC was moderate compared to the ethanol–water extract. Due to potential degradation or transformation of flavonoids under alkaline conditions, TFC could not be reliably quantified in this extract.

Table 1: Main characteristics of the extracts from oak bark.

Extractions	pH	Concentration [g/L]	TPC [mgGAE/g dry extract]	TFC [mgQE/g dry extract]
hot water	4.8±0.3	1,67±0.1	25,1±2,4	33,70±0.2
ethanol-water	5.4±0.2	8,51±0.3	120,88±4,5	95,90±0,5
alkaline	12.2±0.2	16,27±1,6	61,80±2,6	-

3.2 Wood impregnation

The leachability of impregnated products varied notably depending on both the extract type and wood species (Table 2). In general, pine samples exhibited higher leachability than beech among all treatments, reflecting their more porous structure and higher permeability. The water control showed a baseline mass loss due to natural extractives (2.10% in pine and 1.32% in beech). Impregnation with water and ethanol–water extracts led to similar or slightly reduced leaching compared to the control, suggesting moderate fixation of the bioactive compounds within the wood matrix. In contrast, alkaline extracts, despite being neutralized, showed significantly higher leachability, more pronounced in pine than in beech. This is likely due to the higher concentration and solubility of compounds in the alkaline solution, which may not bind as effectively to the wood structure.

Table 2: Main characteristics of the impregnation in wood samples.

Impregnation solution	pH	Concentration [g/L]	Product leachability Pine [%]	Product leachability Beech [%]
Water control	~7.0	-	2.10±0.3	1.32±0.2
water extracts	4.8±0.3	1,67±0.1	1,80±0.4	1,17±0.2
ethanol-water extracts	5.4±0.2	8,51±0.3	2,02±0.4	1,05±0.3
alkaline extracts (neutralized)	6.8±0.3	12,41±0,1	8.45±0.8	5,49±0.7

Moreover, the decay resistance test varied depending on the wood species (Fig. 1). In *P. sylvestris* samples, the ethanol–water extract treatment was effective against both *R. placenta* and *T. versicolor*, resulting in weight losses between 1% and 4%. In *F. sylvatica* samples, no degradation by *R. placenta* was observed with the ethanol–water treatment, while the alkaline extract treatment showed reduced degradation against *T. versicolor* compared to other

treatments.

Figure 1: Representative photographs of impregnated wood samples after exposure to *T. versicolor* and *R. placenta*. Weight loss (WL) percentages indicate the extent of fungal degradation for each treatment group.

4. CONCLUSIONS

These results highlight the potential of ethanol–water bark extracts as effective antifungal treatments, particularly in softwoods. Although alkaline extracts showed higher leachability, their moderate performance suggests promise with further formulation improvements. Overall, this research demonstrates that waste bark is a promising feedstock for sustainable wood protection, offering a viable alternative to conventional preservatives. However, further optimization of extraction, impregnation, and formulation strategies is needed to improve fixation and durability under exposure conditions.

5. REFERENCES

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6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Rene Herrera Diaz thanks the Grant RYC2022-035782-I funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ESF+, and to the financial support from the Basque Country government in the frame of consolidated groups (IT-1690-22).